

The mediating role of Mentalizing between Attachment and Eating Disorders

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Author's note: This study was funded by a scholarship from the Department of Education, Universities and Research of the Basque Government (BFI-2010-294).

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Abstract

The objective of the study was to investigate whether mindfulness mediated the relationship between attachment and Eating Disorders in a sample of 323 female university students and 38 anorexic inpatients using Structural Equation Modelling. All insecure attachment subscales were positively related to Eating Disorder symptoms and negatively to mindfulness. Furthermore, mindfulness scores were negatively associated with Eating Disorder symptoms. Mediation analyses showed that the relationship between all the insecure attachment subscales and Eating Disorders was partially mediated by the mindfulness effects. Our results are in line with Bateman and Fonagy's theory (2004) that implies a mediating role of mindfulness used as a proxy for mentalizing between attachment and psychopathology. Further research is needed, however, to replicate these findings.

Keywords: Attachment, Mentalizing, Mindfulness, Eating Disorders, Mediation

The relatively high prevalence of bulimia nervosa (BN) and anorexia nervosa (AN) in the general population with estimates around 1% and 1.5% respectively, and both the direct and indirect health costs of eating disorder (ED) patients, represent a huge problem for contemporary health care (Hudson, Hiripi, Pope & Kessler, 2007).

Both AN and BN are characterized by their high severity, chronicity, long-term consequences and high mortality (Attia, 2010; Fairburn & Harrison, 2003). Numerous factors have been implicated in the etiology and maintenance of EDs, including sociocultural factors (e.g. pressure to conform to the thin ideal), biological factors (e.g. pubertal timing), and psychological factors (e.g. body dissatisfaction), (Stice, 2002).

In recent years, Fonagy and colleagues have argued that impairments in the capacity for mentalizing might play a key role in eating disorders (Skårderud & Fonagy, 2012). Mentalizing is defined as the mental process by which an individual implicitly and explicitly interprets the actions of himself/herself and others as meaningful on the basis of intentional mental states, such as personal desires, needs, feelings, beliefs, and reasons (Bateman & Fonagy, 2004).

This capacity is deeply rooted in attachment relationships. Indeed, studies suggest that secure attachment typically fosters the development of mentalizing (Fonagy, Target, Steele & Steele, 1998), affect regulation, and self-control. By contrast, insecure attachment experiences and more general adversity typically disrupt the capacity for mentalizing and, linked to this, the development of a coherent self-structure (Bateman & Fonagy, 2008). The proposed developmental model suggests that in the absence of secure early attachment, the capacity to mentalize develops inadequately. In turn, this deficit plays an important role in the onset of various psychiatric disorders involving pathology of the self, such as BPD (Fossati, Feeney, Maffei & Borroni, 2011) antisocial personality disorder, and depression (Bateman & Fonagy, 2012; Bateman & Fonagy, 2004; Sharp, Fonagy & Goodyer, 2008).

This conceptualization seems to imply a mediating role of mentalizing deficits in the relationship between insecure early attachment and psychopathology.

EDs have been conceptualized, based on the mentalizing approach, as involving high levels of insecure attachment and mentalizing deficits, reflecting serious impairments with mentalizing as a cause and/or consequence of the disorder (Skårderud, 2007). However, this assumption has not been empirically studied.

To date, the scarce research carried out in the field of mentalizing in EDs has been mainly based on the Reflective Functioning Scale (RF; Fonagy et al., 1998) a broad measure of mentalizing that is typically scored on interviews such as the Adult Attachment Interview (AAI; George, Kaplan & Main, 1985). Fonagy et al. (1996) for instance, reported that patients with an ED had significantly lower levels of reflective functioning as scored on the Adult Attachment Interview (AAI; George et al., 1985) compared to those with other Axis I disorders (i.e., depression, anxiety, substance abuse) and to a normal control group. Similar results were reported by Ward et al. (2001) in individuals with EDs and their mothers. Similarly, a more recent study found that anorexia nervosa patients assessed using the RF scale and SCORS (Westen, Lohr, Silk, Kerber, & Goodrich, 1990) exhibited significantly lower levels of mentalizing and a significantly lower quality of current relationships with their parents compared with non-ED controls (Rothschild-Yakar, Levy-Shiff, Fridman-Balaban, Gur & Stein, 2010).

Over the years, the RF scale has proved to be a reliable measure of the mentalizing construct, whose scores are independent of personality, verbal intelligence, and educational level (Steele & Steele, 2008). However, mentalizing is increasingly viewed as a multidimensional capacity (Luyten, Fonagy, Lowyck & Vermote, 2012). Indeed, this multi-dimensional construct that can be characterized and organized along 4 polarities: explicit-implicit, cognitive-affective, internal-external and self-other focused (Fonagy & Luyten,

2010; Fonagy & Luyten, 2009). While implicit mentalizing refers to unconscious, automatic or procedural operations employed to imagine mental states, explicit mentalizing involves deliberated and conscious attempts to do this; it can also be centered on cognitive processes or on affective states; internally-based mentalizing requires focusing on thoughts, feelings and internal experiences, while externally-based mentalizing refers to mental processes that are based on visible physical characteristics and actions; and finally, and with respect to objects, it can be self-centered or other centered (Choi-Kain & Gunderson, 2008). Some authors argue that effective mentalizing involves a balance between these dimensions (Fonagy & Luyten, 2010; Fonagy & Luyten, 2009). Several studies have indeed shown that different types of psychopathology are characterized by having different impairments in these dimensions or combinations of them (Allen, Fonagy, & Bateman, 2008; Fonagy & Luyten, 2010; Fonagy & Luyten, 2009).

Based on these psychometric considerations and on the degree of overlap of the mentalizing construct with other constructs (particularly mindfulness), it has recently been proposed to use self-report measures of mindfulness (and related constructs) as indirect but easy-to-use proxy measures of impairments in mentalizing (Choi-Kain & Gunderson, 2008). Despite the differences between these two concepts, some authors suggest that there is a wide variety of measures (namely MAAS) that tap into different aspects or dimensions of mentalizing and that can be used as an operationalization of them. These self-report measures permit the study of mentalizing-related phenomena in large samples (Luyten et al., 2012).

Mindfulness is generally defined and characterized by the ability to maintain a nonjudgmental attention to, and acceptance of, present-moment experiences (Baer, Smith, Hopkins, Krietemeyer & Toney, 2006; Bishop et al., 2004; Brown & Ryan, 2004). Indeed, both mindfulness and mentalizing involve directing one's attention to one's own experience in a way that mitigates tendencies towards impulsivity and reactivity. Both constructs also

emphasize the integration of cognitive and affective aspects of mental states in encouraging simultaneous recognition and participation in internal experience (Choi-Kain & Gunderson, 2008). However, mindfulness overlaps only with explicit mentalizing processes that are focused on the self (Walling, 2007). In order to further clarify the relationships between mindfulness and mentalizing, Walling (2007) recently made a compelling case for the view that mindfulness is the essential starting place from which genuine mentalizing can arise; not all mindful individuals are expected to be reflective, but reflective functioning at the moderate-to-high level cannot happen without mindfulness (Fossati et al., 2011).

Interestingly, recent studies suggest that low mindfulness may underlie ED difficulties. Lavender, Jardin and Anderson (2009), for instance, found significant negative associations between mindfulness and bulimic symptoms in a non-clinical sample. Masuda and Wendell (2010) reported, in turn, that mindfulness (or psychological flexibility) and disordered eating cognitions were inversely related. More specifically, using the Five Facet Mindfulness Questionnaire, Lavender, Gratz and Tull (2011) showed that four facets of mindfulness (Awareness, Non reactivity, Non judgment and Describing) were uniquely associated with eating pathology above and beyond anxiety and depression symptoms. Finally, impairments in mindfulness have been suggested to be key factors in explaining the effects of interventions with ED patients, as both initial levels upon admission to residential ED treatment, and improvements in mindfulness at discharge, have been related to ED symptomatology (Butryn et al., 2013).

In relation to attachment, research has indeed shown a greater prevalence of insecure attachment in the eating disordered population than in non-clinical groups (Ward et al., 2001; Zachrisson & Skårderud, 2010), although EDs have not been shown to be specifically related to a single insecure attachment style. It is also important to note, in this context, that mindfulness, as mentalizing, has been related to insecure attachment experiences (Cordon &

Finney, 2008); in particular, low levels of attachment anxiety have been associated with higher levels of mindfulness (Walsh, Balint, Smolira, Fredericksen & Madsen, 2009). Furthermore, more recent studies have also shown that attachment security was related to dispositional mindfulness (Goodall, Trejnowska & Darling, 2012).

Given the paucity of studies about the role that specific mentalizing deficits could play in the onset or maintenance of EDs, and the fact that the possible mediating role of mentalizing between insecure early attachment and ED symptoms has not already been empirically tested, more research is needed to clarify the relationship between all these constructs.

Based on the above considerations, the aims of this study were:

a) To use the concept of mindfulness to operationalize and measure some of the components of the mentalizing construct (Bateman & Fonagy, 2004; Walling, 2007).

b) To test the hypothesis that mindfulness substantially mediates the relationships between insecure attachment patterns and eating disorders in a sample comprising Spanish non-clinical university women and eating disordered women diagnosed with anorexia nervosa.

First, we tested whether insecure attachment patterns were significantly associated with low mindfulness; next, we evaluated whether insecure attachment patterns were significantly related to eating disorder symptoms; then, we tested whether mindfulness was significantly linked to eating disorder features. Finally, we carried out formal mediation analyses.

The theoretical model is depicted in Figure 1.

Methods

Participants and procedures

The *ED sample* comprised 38 female inpatients aged 13 to 30 years. The mean age was 21.9 ($SD=5.30$). All them were receiving psychological treatment in the Basque Public Health System and in different national treatment associations and met the criteria for a full-blown *DSM-IV* (American Psychiatric Association, 1994) diagnosis of anorexia (AN-restrictive or purgative).

The *control sample* was composed of 323 female university students from different faculties at the University of the Basque Country (Spain). The mean age of participants was 19.1 ($SD=1.94$), and 97.5% had Spanish nationality. All participants were Caucasian and from middle-class backgrounds.

A comparison of the 2 study groups' demographic characteristics revealed no significant differences for a number of relevant variables such as nationality (ED sample: 97.4% Spanish, non-patients: 97.7%), familial composition (ED sample: 86.8% intact families, 10.5% divorced parents, 2.7% parental loss, nonpatients: 83.3% intact families, 10.5% divorced parents, 5% parental loss), father's education (ED sample: $M= 3.97\pm 1.62$, nonpatients: $M= 4.12\pm 1.50$), mother's education (ED sample: $M= 4.00\pm 1.39$, nonpatients: $M= 4.03\pm 1.44$) and number of siblings (ED sample: $M= 1.71\pm 1.18$, nonpatients: $M= 1.84\pm 0.95$). However, differences were observed in terms of age (ED sample: $M= 21.90\pm 5.30$, nonpatients: $M= 19.91\pm 1.95$), $t(359)= 4.6$, $p=.027$) and academic education (ED sample: $M= 5.00\pm 1.40$, nonpatients: $M= 6\pm 0.00$), $t(359)= - 5.42$, $p<.000$. As expected, a significant between-group difference emerged for body mass index BMI (AN sample: $M= 19.19\pm 2.58$, nonpatients: $M= 21.32\pm 2.90$), $t(358)= - 4.3$, $p<.000$.

Study procedures were approved by the local ethics committee of Deusto University.

Participants in the control sample completed the packet of questionnaires during regular classes. The study was presented as a study on health and emotions. The information was neutral and did not disclose anything about the aims of the study. Students had the opportunity to withhold participation at any moment during the assessment. Only two participants dropped out during the course of it.

All participants in the ED sample and their parents in the case of minors under age 18, gave their written informed consent to participate in the study. The study protocol was presented to the Scientific Ethical Committee and the Supervising Board of the centres, neither of whom had further remarks on the subject.

Materials

Participants completed the following questionnaires:

Attachment. Attachment was assessed by the Spanish version (Versión reducida del cuestionario CaMir; Balluerka, Lacasa, Gorostiaga, Muela, & Pierrehumbert, 2011) of the Cartes, Modèles Individuels de Relation (CAMIR; Pierrehumbert et al., 1996). The questionnaire comprises 32 items evaluating 5 dimensions of attachment and 2 dimensions of family functioning. Because in the study we were only interested in the insecure attachment itself, only Preoccupation, Parental Interference, Self-Sufficiency and Childhood Trauma were included:

(a) *Preoccupation* involves separation anxiety from the loved ones and an excessive preoccupation for attachment figures (e.g. “I’m always afraid of hurting those who are close to me when I leave them”); (b) *Parental Interference* refers to the memory of being overprotected in childhood, to having been a fearful child, and to having been concerned about being abandoned (e.g., “My parents couldn’t help themselves from controlling everything: my appearance, my performance at school or even my friends”); (c) *Self-*

Sufficiency and Resentment towards the parents involves rejection of feelings of dependence and reciprocity, and anger towards loved ones (e.g., “ I only count on myself to solve the problems I have”); and (d) *Childhood Trauma* includes memories of having experienced unavailability, violence, and threats from attachment figures during childhood (e.g., “When I was a child, there were unbearable fights at home”), taking into account past and present attachment experiences and family functioning. Participants were asked to rate on a five-point Likert scale from 1 (*strongly disagree*) to 5 (*strongly agree*) to what extent they agreed with each item. The first two subscales are theoretically related to descriptions of preoccupied attachment, the third subscale overlaps with avoidant attachment and the fourth relates descriptions of disorganized attachment. The questionnaire has acceptable psychometric properties (Balluerka et al., 2011). In the present study alpha values ranged from .55 to .84.

Mentalizing. Consistent with theoretical views arguing for conceptual overlap between mindfulness and some core features of mentalizing, the Mindfulness Attention and Awareness Scale (MAAS; Brown & Ryan, 2003) was used as a proxy measure for that. The MAAS is a 15-item unidimensional measure of trait mindfulness, that assesses the quality of attention and awareness that individuals apply to their daily lives.

Although all the items of the MAAS are defined in a negative direction (“I could be experiencing some emotion and not be conscious of it until some time later”, “It seems I am running on automatic without much awareness of what I am doing”), the six-point Likert scale is arranged such that higher scores reflect more mindfulness. Participants are asked to rate their level of agreement with the statements in a 6 point Likert scale from 1 (almost always) to 6 (almost never). The Spanish version of the MAAS has demonstrated high internal consistency 0.90 (Soler et al., 2009). In the present study the Cronbach’s value of the MAAS was also 0.90.

Eating Disorder Symptoms. Eating disorder symptoms were assessed with the Eating Attitudes Test–26 (EAT-26; Garner, Olmsted, Bohr, & Garfinkel, 1982), a 26-item measure which evaluates attitudes and behaviour associated with anorexia and bulimia nervosa.

The items assess three types of ED symptoms: *Dieting*, (e.g., “I am terrified about being overweight”), *Bulimia and food preoccupation* (e.g., “I have gone on eating binges where I feel I may not be able to stop”, and *Oral control* (e.g., “I avoid eating when I am hungry”). Items are scored on a 6-point Likert-type scale from 1 (ever) to 6 (always), higher scores indicating greater eating pathology. The EAT-26 has been found to exhibit strong psychometric properties and correlates highly with eating disorder status and other widely used eating disorder measures (Miller, Schmidt, Vaillancourt, McDougall & Laliberte, 2006). The Spanish version of the EAT-26 showed good psychometric properties (Castro, Toro, Salamero & Guimara, 1991). In the present sample, Cronbach’s alpha for the total score was 0.84.

Statistical Analysis

Zero-order correlations were calculated to explore the relationships among the study variables. Next, SEM was used to investigate the theoretical model presented in Figure 1 following state of the art recommendations for the testing of mediation models (Fairchild & MacKinnon, 2009; Hayes, 2009; Hoyle & Smith, 1994), in a two-step strategy. In the first step, the theoretical model was tested, with only the indirect paths included, in which the MAAS scale fully mediated the relationship between attachment subscales (Preoccupation, Parental Interference, Self-Sufficiency and Childhood Trauma) and Eating Disorders.

[Figure 1]

Non-significant paths were deleted, yielding the final base model.

In a second step a model adding all the direct paths from the different attachment dimensions to Eating Disorders was tested. Non-significant paths were deleted, leading to the final model (see Figure 2).

If the final base model (the more parsimonious one) did not provide a significantly worse fit than the final model (model with the indirect and direct effects), this indicates full mediation; else, the MAAS scale is a partial mediator in the association between attachment and eating disorder symptoms. The following fit indices were used: χ^2/df , CFI, and RMSEA. The following cut-off values were used: $\chi^2/df \leq 3$, CFI $>.90$ indicating acceptable fit and $>.95$ indicating good fit (Hu & Bentler, 1999; Kline, 1998) and RMSEA < 0.08 (acceptable fit) and < 0.06 (good fit) (Byrne, 1998; Hu & Bentler, 1999). To compare the fit of the nested models (e.g., with and without direct effects), we used χ^2 - difference tests.

Results

Zero-order correlations

As Table 1 indicates, all the insecure attachment subscales were, as expected, negatively related to mentalizing features as assessed with the MAAS. Specifically Preoccupation negatively correlated with MAAS ($r=-.16$, $p<.01$), as happened with Interference and MAAS ($r=-.38$, $p<.01$), Self-sufficiency and MAAS ($r=-.38$, $p<.01$), and Childhood Trauma and MAAS ($r=-.35$, $p<.01$). Moreover, all the insecure attachment subscales were positively related to eating disorder symptoms: Preoccupation and Dieting ($r=.14$, $p<.01$), Bulimia and Food Preoccupation ($r=.13$, $p<.05$), and Oral Control ($r=.22$, $p<.01$); Interference and Dieting ($r=.31$, $p<.01$), Bulimia and Food Preoccupation ($r=.30$, $p<.01$), and Oral Control ($r=.25$, $p<.01$); Self-sufficiency and Dieting ($r=.30$, $p<.01$),

Bulimia and Food Preoccupation ($r=.28$, $p<.01$), and Oral Control ($r=.23$, $p<.01$); Trauma and Dieting ($r=.24$, $p<.01$), Bulimia and Food Preoccupation ($r=.23$, $p<.01$), and Oral Control ($r=.15$, $p<.01$),

Finally, mentalizing as assessed with the MAAS was, as expected, highly negatively correlated with eating disorder symptoms. Specifically MAAS negatively correlated with Dieting ($r=-.38$, $p<.01$), Bulimia and Food Preoccupation ($r=-.37$, $p<.01$), and Oral Control ($r=-.23$, $p<.01$). Hence, conditions for mediation were met for all the insecure attachment subscales (Preoccupation, Interference, Self-sufficiency, and Trauma) and for MAAS.

[Table 1]

Structural Equation Modeling

The theoretical model (Figure 1) did not provide a good fit to the data; $\chi^2 = 460.71$ $p < .000$; $df=16$; $\chi^2/df = 28.79$, CFI = .473, RMSEA = .278. In this model, only the path from Preoccupation to MAAS was not significant.

AMOS suggested adding three error covariance, namely between the errors of Dieting and Bulimia and Food Preoccupation, Bulimia and Food Preoccupation and Oral Control, and Dieting and Oral Control, most probably because of the similar formulation of the items. This led to the final base model which already provided a relatively good fit to the data, $\chi^2 = 36.57$, $p < .000$; $df=13$; $\chi^2/df = 2.81$, CFI = .972; RMSEA = .071.

The model adding all the direct paths did not provide a good fit to the data; $\chi^2 = 394.32$ $p < .000$; $df=4$; $\chi^2/df = 98.58$, CFI = .538, RMSEA = .521. In this model, several paths were not significant, namely from Preoccupation to Dieting and to Bulimia and Food Preoccupation; Self-Sufficiency to Dieting, Bulimia and Food Preoccupation and Oral Control and finally, Childhood Trauma to Dieting and to Bulimia and Food Preoccupation. We therefore dropped

these paths. This led to the final model (Figure 2) which had a good fit: $\chi^2 = 12.67$, $p = .024$; $df=10$; $\chi^2/df = 1.26$, $CFI = .997$; $RMSEA = .027$. Next, this final model was compared to the model with only the indirect paths (final base model). The test showed significant differences between the models ($\Delta\chi^2 = 23.90$, $df=3$, $p < 0.00$), implying that the final model with a better fit (Figure 2) explained the data better.

Discussion

Eating disorders have recently started to be understood as disorders of the self characterized by impairments in mentalizing (Skårderud & Fonagy, 2012), although little research has been done to address the specific difficulties in EDs concerning mentalizing. This study sought to further investigate the role of mindfulness, namely the capacity to be attentive or cognitively aware of psychological processes or states, taken as an operationalization of impairments in mentalizing in the relationship between attachment and Eating Disorders.

Zero order correlations showed that all the insecure attachment dimensions (Preoccupation, Parental Interference, Self-Sufficiency and Trauma) were highly negatively correlated with the MAAS as a descriptor of mentalizing capacity. These findings are consistent with several studies that have previously demonstrated associations between attachment and features of mindfulness (Cordon & Finney, 2008) and they are in line with theoretical formulation within the mentalizing approach (Bateman & Fonagy, 2008; Skårderud & Fonagy, 2012). In particular, attachment security has been positively related to dispositional mindfulness (Goodall et al., 2012) whereas in relation to attachment insecurity, attachment anxiety (but not attachment avoidance) was found to be negatively related to

mindfulness (Walsh et al., 2009). Siegel (2001) suggested that differences in maternal interaction style may play a mediating role in the simultaneous development of both emotion regulation and mindfulness. Thus, higher mindfulness in mothers could result in the mother attending more receptively to the infant's needs and emotional states which would simultaneously promote secure attachment and mindfulness in the child. In spite of some differences in theoretical assumptions, these findings are in line with mentalizing theory and findings, according to which secure attachment and mentalizing are facilitated in children when mothers foster an interpretation of their own actions and their children's in psychological terms (Fonagy & Target, 1997; Meins, Fernyhough, Fradley & Tuckey, 2001; Meins et al., 2002; Peterson & Slaughter, 2003; C. Sharp, Fonagy & Goodyer, 2006; Slade, Grienenberger, Bernbach, Levy & Locker, 2005). In fact, mother's mentalizing responses seem to enhance the child's emotion regulation; at the same time, the child consolidates an attachment secure bond. This bond facilitates children's mentalizing capacity (Lanza, 2011).

Zero order correlations also showed that the capacity to be attentive or cognitively aware of psychological processes or states, was strongly negatively associated with ED symptoms (Dieting, Bulimia and Food Preoccupation and Oral Control). These results are in line with other studies reporting an inverse relationship between mindfulness and bulimic symptoms (Lavender et al., 2009) and disordered eating cognitions (Masuda & Wendell, 2010), even when controlling for anxiety and depression (Lavender et al., 2011).

Analyses using Structural Equation Modelling shed further light on the dynamics of the relationship between attachment, mindfulness and eating disorders. These analyses supported the hypothesis that impairments in cognitive attention to internal mental states as assessed with the MAAS, mediated the relationship between insecure attachment styles and eating disorder symptoms. In other words, results of this study suggest that insecure

attachment is related to eating disorder symptoms through impairments in the capacity to direct one's attention or consciousness to present reality (Brown & Ryan, 2003).

Findings concerning Preoccupation and Parental Interference are in line with which some authors have called attachment anxiety or attachment hyperactivating strategies (Brennan, Clark & Shaver, 1998). Anxiously attached individuals are known to be hypervigilant to cues of rejection and abandonment and often show high levels of rumination concerning stressful thoughts and experiences (Mikulincer & Florian, 1998). High levels of mentalizing, by contrast, are associated with a relaxation of attention to negative experiences, much as has been described in the mindfulness literature, i.e. that high levels of mindfulness are characterized by low levels of monitoring the environment for threat signals and rumination. Moreover, anxiously attached individuals have a great need of control and are less tolerant of ambiguity and unexpected experiences (Hazan & Shaver, 1987) so they tend to resist information that fails to confirm their expectations (Mikulincer & Arad, 1999), whereas mindfulness is associated with greater cognitive flexibility and openness (Brown & Ryan, 2003).

The role of Self-Sufficiency and Childhood Trauma in predicting low levels of mindfulness could be explained due to its similarities with avoidant attachment or attachment deactivating strategies. In fact, traumatic experiences such as unavailability, violence and threats of attachment figures as assessed by Childhood Trauma, or rejection of feelings of dependence and reciprocity, and anger towards loved ones as measured with the Self Sufficiency scale, may lead the child to a defensive retreat of the mental world, a defensive avoidance of his/her own and the others' internal experiences as they are too threatening to consider. Avoidant attachment or under-activating style conveys these ideas as it has been defined as characterized by thought suppression (the process of deliberately trying to stop thinking about certain thoughts; Wegner, 1989), defensive projection and cognitive closure

(the human desire to eliminate ambiguity and arrive at definite conclusions) (Mikulincer & Florian, 1998). Yet, childhood trauma may also be associated with attachment hyperactivating styles, leading to anxious preoccupation with loss at the expense of awareness of internal mental states.

Together, results of this study suggest that a capacity to reflect about the self, based on non-judgmental awareness of the present moment experience, including one's sensations, thoughts, and bodily states, may facilitate a more accepting stance and therefore help counter the processes which are associated with eating disorder symptoms (Park, Dunn, & Barnard, 2012). The inability to do so, appears to be incompatible with present moment, non-judgmental experiencing which has been associated with psychological well being (Shapiro, Oman, Thoresen, Plante & Flinders, 2008). In fact, mindfulness has been considered by some authors as an essential capacity that form the basis for more complex mentalizing processes due to the receptivity by which it is characterized (Walling, 2007). In any case, results suggest that mindfulness should be considered an important target in the understanding and treatment of eating disorders.

In summary, this study makes a contribution to the literature by documenting the relationship between insecure attachment, mindfulness as a proxy of impairments self-cognitive mentalizing deficits and eating disorder symptoms.

The present research should be considered in the light of the study's limitations. First, as noted, the cross sectional and correlational nature of the data limits the ability to draw causal conclusions. For example, although attachment insecurity can contribute to diminishing cognitive awareness and consequently increase the likelihood to develop eating disorder attitudes and behaviours, it may also be that those eating disorder symptoms negatively impact upon cognitive awareness and foster insecurity in attachment relationships.

Therefore, future research should prospectively examine carefully how these deficits develop and relate to symptomatology.

Secondly, the study relied only on self-report measures, which may be associated with reporting bias. Future research with other validated measures of attachment and mindfulness is recommended, for example, interview-based or observation measures.

Thirdly, more research is needed to disentangle similarities and differences between the concept of embodied mentalizing and mindfulness, although both clearly seem to overlap theoretically.

Additionally, more uniformity in terms of age and educational level between the ED sample and the nonpatient sample would have been desirable, or even replicating the study with a larger ED sample would strengthen the results. Finally, future studies should also account for time under treatment in the ED sample. Some may maintain that those who have been under therapy, may have better levels of mindfulness and introspection.

Notwithstanding these limitations, the findings of the current study contribute to a relatively small literature on the association between attachment, mentalizing and eating pathology and highlight the potential utility of targeting these aspects in the prevention and treatment of EDs and related pathology.

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	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	<i>M (SD)</i>
1. Preoccupation	—								3.11 (0.39)
2. Interference	,20**	—							2.29 (0.81)
3. Self-sufficiency	,12*	,40**	—						2.72 (0.72)
4. Trauma	,01	,32**	,48**	—					1.46 (0.61)
5. MAAS	-,16**	-,38**	-,38**	-,35**	—				65.16(12.1)
6. Dieting	,14**	,31**	,30**	,24**	-,38**	—			5.73 (7.81)

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Table 1. Zero Order Correlations, Means and Standard Deviations

7. Bulimia	,13*	,30**	,28**	,23**	-,37**	,76**	_	1.68 (2.85)
8. Oral Control	,22**	,25**	,23**	,15**	-,23**	,60**	,56**	2.48 (3.74)

* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$

Figure 1. Theoretical model

Figure 1. Theoretical model of the relationships between Attachment (Preoccupation, Parental Interference, Self-Sufficiency, Childhood Trauma), Mindfulness (MAAS) and Eating Disorder Symptoms (Dieting, Bulimia and Food Preoccupation and Oral Control) Standardized values are given for the path coefficients *** $p < .001$.

Figure 1. Theoretical model

Figure 1. Theoretical model of the relationships between Attachment (Preoccupation, Parental Interference, Self-Sufficiency, Childhood Trauma), Mindfulness (MAAS) and Eating Disorder Symptoms (Dieting, Bulimia and Food Preoccupation and Oral Control) Relationships between the variables are represented by (+) and (-) respectively.

Figure 2. Final model

Figure 2. Final model

Standardized values are given for the path coefficients *** $p < .001$.

Table 1. Zero Order Correlations, Means and Standard Deviations

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	<i>M (SD)</i>
1. Preoccupation	—								3.11 (0.39)
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* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$